

PREVALENCE OF HYPOTHYROIDISM AMONG OBESE PATIENTS

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Abstract

Background: The prevalence of hypothyroidism in obese populations is a public health concern that needs immediate attention. The connection between obesity and hypothyroidism is crucial for public health policy, as early intervention.

Objective: To determine the prevalence of hypothyroidism in obese patients and to identify clinical and demographic factors associated with these two conditions.

Methods: This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at Sharif Medical City Hospital in Lahore from January 2025 to June 2025. A total of 115 obese patients were enrolled using non-probability consecutive sampling. Obesity was confirmed with body mass index ($> 30\text{kg}/\text{m}^2$). Demographic and clinical data were collected. Blood samples were collected to measure the TSH, T3, and T4 levels.

Results: The overall prevalence of hypothyroidism was 68.70%. Among obese patients ($\text{BMI} > 30\text{kg}/\text{m}^2$), the prevalence was significantly higher at 75.64%, compared to (55.56%) in patients ($\text{BMI} \geq 40\text{kg}/\text{m}^2$). Hypothyroidism was also significantly associated with diabetes ($p = 0.034$), abnormal thyroid gland ($p = 0.000$), and BMI ($p = 0.047$). Additionally, mean TSH (5.78 ± 2.76) was high and mean values of T3 and T4 ($0.62 \pm 0.54\text{ ng}/\text{mL}$ and $4.56 \pm 2.71\text{ }\mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$) were below the normal ranges. A significant majority (68.7%) had abnormal thyroid gland findings, correlating with the high TSH and low T3/T4 values.

Conclusion: It is concluded that hypothyroidism is alarmingly prevalent among obese patients, particularly among patients with abnormal thyroid gland findings. These findings highlight the need for early screening and intervention, especially in patients with elevated BMI. Further research is needed to explore the mechanisms underlying this relationship and to establish optimal management strategies for obese patients with hypothyroidism.

INTRODUCTION

Hypothyroidism, a condition characterized by thyroid hormone deficiency, is a prevalent endocrine disorder with widespread health implications [1]. Thyroid hormones are vital for regulating basal metabolism,

thermogenesis, and metabolic processes, including lipid and glucose metabolism, food intake, and fat oxidation [2]. These hormones significantly influence the body's energy balance and its ability to maintain

homeostasis [3]. A deficiency in thyroid hormones leads to reduced energy expenditure, fluid retention, and altered metabolic functions, which contribute to a broad spectrum of health issues, including cardiovascular disease and increased mortality risk [4,5].

Obesity and hypothyroidism frequently coexist, with studies showing that obesity can either exacerbate thyroid dysfunction or result from it [6]. The relationship between the two has gained considerable attention in recent years, with emerging evidence suggesting that obesity might not only be a consequence of thyroid dysfunction but also a contributing factor to its onset [7]. The mechanisms by which hypothyroidism affects body weight, body composition, and metabolism remain an area of active research [8]. Specifically, hypothyroidism leads to significant changes in resting energy expenditure (REE), body temperature, and total energy expenditure, independent of physical activity levels, making it a crucial factor in understanding obesity's complex etiology [9].

Hypothyroidism has varying prevalence throughout the globe, with estimations of having 3-10 percent of the population affected by thyroid diseases [10]. In Pakistan, the incidence rate of hypothyroidism is stated as 4.1%, which demonstrates the clinical importance of the disorder in the country [11]. The prevalence of hypothyroidism in obese populations has been examined in numerous studies that underscore its importance as a health challenge to the population. Souza et al. revealed that 3.5-7.4 percent of obese patients had hypothyroidism which leads to a significant relationship between the thyroid dysfunction and obesity [12]. According to a study conducted in Mexico, Sosa-Lopez et al., showed that 10.7 percent of obese patients had hypothyroidism, further confirming the relevance of awareness and early diagnosis in this high-risk population [13]. The association between obesity and hypothyroidism is essential to the public health policy, because timely intervention can help to reduce the burden of these two conditions [14]. In Pakistan, there is a significant amount of underdiagnosed or incidentally diagnosed hypothyroid when tested, presenting life-threatening conditions later in life span. Thus, this serious issue needs immediate attention to be added as a regular screening profile. The current study seeks to address

this gap by estimating the prevalence of hypothyroidism among obese patients, with implications for public health policy and clinical practice. Objective

To determine the prevalence of hypothyroidism among obese patients and to identify any significant correlations between the two conditions.

Methodology

This was a descriptive cross-sectional study at Sharif Medical City Hospital, Lahore, from January 2025 to June 2025. A total of 115 patients aged with a Body Mass Index (BMI) of more than $30\text{kg}/\text{m}^2$ were enrolled in the study. Non-probability consecutive sampling was used to recruit eligible participants from the Department of Medicine at Sharif Medical City Hospital.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Adults aged between 18 and 65 years.
- Patient with a Body Mass Index (BMI) of more than $30\text{kg}/\text{m}^2$.
- Informed consent provided.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients on anti-thyroid medication or taking medication that disrupts thyroid levels.
- Special patient populations, such as pregnant women.
- Patients with ongoing critical illnesses such as ischemic heart disease. Chronic renal failure and cirrhosis liver.
- Patients with incomplete medical records or those unwilling to participate.
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Data Collection

After obtaining informed consent, demographic and clinical information were recorded using a structured questionnaire. Variables included name, age, gender, weight (kg), height (cm), diabetes status, and hypertension status. Blood samples (3 ml) were collected in the morning in a plain serum bottle. The drawn samples were labeled and sent to the laboratory of Sharif Medical City Hospital, Lahore, for serum TSH and serum free T₃, T₄ levels. The samples were analyzed on a fully automated hormone analyzer. The reference range for normal serum TSH level is 0.35-4.94 $\mu\text{U}/\text{mL}$, for the serum T₄ it is 4.87 to

11.72 μ g/dL, and T3 values range from 0.64-1.52ng/mL.

Data Analysis

Data were entered into and analyzed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic and clinical variables. Quantitative data (age, BMI, TSH, T3, T4, BSR>200mg/dl, and BP>160/90) were presented in Mean \pm SD, while qualitative data (gender, thyroid examination) were presented as frequency (%). The prevalence of hypothyroidism was calculated as a proportion of confirmed hypothyroidism cases among

all obese patients. Chi-square tests were applied to identify associations between hypothyroidism and potential risk factors. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The study included 115 patients, with a mean age of 40.78 years, ranging from 18 to 65 years. The cohort consisted of 55.7% males and 44.3% females. The average BMI was 34.16, indicating that the patients were obese. Nearly half of the patients (46.1%) had hypertension, while 43.5% were diabetic.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics (n = 115)

Characteristic	Value
Total Patients	115
Mean Age (years)	40.78 \pm 14.4
Gender: Male	64 (55.7%)
Gender: Female	51 (44.3%)
Height (cm)	165.9 \pm 9.46
Weight (kg)	82.3 \pm 21.0
Body Mass Index (BMI)	34.16 \pm 8.42
Diabetes: Yes	50 (43.5%)
Diabetes: No	65 (56.5%)
Hypertension: Yes	53 (46.1%)
Hypertension: No	62 (53.9%)

The thyroid-related measures show that the mean TSH value was 5.78 \pm 2.76, which is above the normal range of 0.35-4.94 μ U/mL. The average values of T3 and T4 (0.62 \pm 0.54 ng/mL and 4.56 \pm

2.71 μ g/dL) are below the reference ranges, which further supports the hypothesis of hypothyroidism in these patients. A significant majority (68.7%) had abnormal thyroid gland findings, correlating with the high TSH and low T3/T4 values.

Table 2: Clinical Measures and Thyroid Gland Examination Findings in Hypothyroidism Patients

TSH	5.78 \pm 2.76
T3	0.62 \pm 0.54
T4	4.56 \pm 2.71
BSR	223 \pm 14.8
Thyroid Gland Examination: Normal	36 (31.3%)
Thyroid Gland Examination: Abnormal	79 (68.7%)

Age ($p = 0.014$) is significantly associated with hypothyroidism, indicating older age may be a risk factor. Diabetes ($p = 0.034$) also showed a significant association with hypothyroidism, which aligns with previous studies suggesting that thyroid dysfunction is common in diabetic patients. Hypertension ($p =$

0.042) is another factor significantly associated with hypothyroidism in this cohort. Obesity, as measured by BMI ($p = 0.047$), is also significantly associated with hypothyroidism. Abnormal thyroid examination findings ($p = 0.000$) are strongly associated with hypothyroidism.

Table 3: Factors associated with Hypothyroidism

Gender	0.426
Age	0.014
Diabetes	0.034
Hypertension	0.042
BMI	0.047
Thyroid Gland Examination	0.000

The prevalence of hypothyroidism was higher in females (72.55%) compared to males (65.62%), which is consistent with literature that shows a higher prevalence of thyroid disorders in women. The highest prevalence of hypothyroidism was observed in the 29-40 years age group (77.42%), followed by those in the 53-65 years range (76.47%). Younger patients (18-28 years) had the lowest prevalence (53.33%). Those with blood sugar levels greater than 200 mg/dL had a slightly lower prevalence (64.62%) of

hypothyroidism compared to those with lower blood sugar levels (74%). Hypertension was associated with a higher prevalence of hypothyroidism, especially those with blood pressure higher than 160/90 (73.58%). Class I obesity (BMI between 30 and <35 kg/m²) had the highest prevalence of hypothyroidism (75.64%), whereas class 2 and class 3 obesity had slightly lower prevalence (52.63% and 55.56% respectively). The overall prevalence of hypothyroidism was 68.70%.

Table 4: Prevalence of Hypothyroidism with Demographic and Clinical Variables

Variable	Hypothyroidism (No)	Hypothyroidism (Yes)	Total	Prevalence (%)
Gender				
Female	14	37	51	72.55
Male	22	42	64	65.62
Diabetes (Blood Sugar)				
> 200 mg/dL	23	42	65	64.62
< 200 mg/dL	13	37	50	74.00
Hypertension (Blood Pressure)				
< 160/90	22	40	62	64.52
> 160/90	14	39	53	73.58
BMI				
Class I Obesity (30 to < 35 kg/m ²)	19	59	78	75.64
Class 2 Obesity (35 to < 40 kg/m ²)	9	10	19	52.63
Class 3 Obesity (≥ 40 kg/m ²)	8	10	18	55.56
Age Group				
18-28 years	14	16	30	53.33

29-40 years	7	24	31	77.42
41-52 years	7	13	20	65.00
53-65 years	8	26	34	76.47
Total cases of Hypothyroidism	36	79	115	68.70

Prevalence of Hypothyroidism by Age Group

Prevalence of Hypothyroidism by Diabetes

Prevalence of Hypothyroidism by Hypertension

Prevalence of Hypothyroidism by BMI (Obesity)

Discussion

This study assessed the prevalence of hypothyroidism in obese patients at Sharif Medical City Hospital in Lahore, and identified clinical and demographic factors associated. The prevalence of hypothyroidism in obese individuals has been extensively studied in various regions. In our study, the prevalence of hypothyroidism was highest among those with Class I obesity (BMI 30–35 kg/m²), with 75.64% of patients exhibiting hypothyroid symptoms. Similar trends were observed in studies from Mexico and India, where the association between obesity and hypothyroidism was also strong. The study by Sosa-López et al. (2021) found that 10.7% of obese individuals had hypothyroidism, supporting the notion that thyroid dysfunction is prevalent among those with high BMI [13].

The current study identified significant associations between hypothyroidism and conditions such as diabetes and hypertension, with p-values of 0.034 and 0.042, respectively. This aligns with findings in other studies, including the one by Shaphe et al. (2023), which explored the relationship between obesity and hypothyroidism and noted similar associations [15]. Hypothyroidism can exacerbate metabolic disorders like diabetes, as thyroid hormones play a critical role in glucose metabolism. Similarly, Malik et al. (2025) determined the prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism approximately 16% [16]. Also, the proportion of hypothyroidism (12.8%) among the obese patients was found in a recent study [17].

This study's findings reported that hypothyroidism was significantly prevalent among women (72.55%) compared with men (65.62%), which is in agreement with the global trend. Epidemiological data indicate that hormonal changes in menopause and pregnancy, as well as other factors related to gender influence, may significantly contribute to the increased predisposition of women. The prevalence of hypothyroidism was highest among patients within the age range of 29-40 years, which is also justified by the observation of many previous studies that it is more likely to be observed within the middle-aged adult population [18]. The average serum TSH levels were high (5.78±2.76 µIU/mL) above the upper limit of the normal range, but the serum T3 and T4 levels were significantly lower, which confirms the diagnosis of hypothyroidism. These findings confirm those

presented by Dharia et al. (2025), who found that the thyroid hormone imbalance is prevalent in obesity populations [4]. Specifically, low serum T3 and high serum TSH indicate compensatory processes in which the thyroid and gland is trying to preserve euthyroidism by producing insufficient thyroid hormones. The research thus promotes the need to screen for thyroid in obese patients routinely because early diagnosis and management of thyroid disorders can mitigate related cardiovascular, metabolic, and weight risks. Early-stage intervention, promoted by Wilson (2021), is crucial to enhancing metabolic health among obese groups and alleviating complications of thyroid dysfunction [19].

Conclusion

It is concluded that the high prevalence of hypothyroidism (68.7%) in obese patients, highlights the need for regular screening and early intervention, especially in patients with elevated BMI. The findings suggest that obesity exacerbates thyroid dysfunction, with notable associations with diabetes, hypertension, and abnormal thyroid gland findings. Further research is needed to explore the mechanisms underlying this relationship and to establish optimal management strategies for obese patients with hypothyroidism.

Author Contribution

Author read and approved the final version.

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